

ABSTRACT

This descriptive-comparative and correlational study aimed to determine the profile and coping behaviors of high school students in a public secondary school in the division of Iloilo. The findings indicate that students possessed effective coping behaviors regardless of their profile. Regarding the difference in the coping behaviors of the students, this study revealed a significant difference in the coping behaviors of students and their grades and sex. Regarding the relationship, all variables were significant except for the student's grades.

Keywords: *Coping Behaviors, High School Students, Intact Family, Disrupted Family*

INTRODUCTION

Research on families has a long history that has expanded rapidly over the years. Its primary goal is to understand families better so that the quality of life may be enhanced. To better understand society and social life, it is essential to know the family, the nucleus of civilization. Burgess and Locke (1963, cited in Zulueta, 2002) defined the family as a group of persons united by bonds of marriage, blood, or adoption, constituting a single household, interacting and communicating with each other in their respective social roles of husband and wife, father and mother, son and daughter, brother and sister, and creating and maintaining a common culture.

Most people spend a significant portion of their lives in the family. The family is the oldest and most fundamental of all social institutions. From the beginning of human life, people have grouped themselves into families to find emotional, physical, and communal support.

The Filipino family, during the Spanish period and before the outbreak of World War II, preserved its solidarity. Family ties were close. The members lived, worked, and prayed as a family. As the head of the family, the father worked hard to provide the bare essentials: food, shelter, clothing, and education. On the other hand, the mother looked after the family's physical, social, emotional, religious, and educational needs. The children were raised to obey and respect their parents and care for them in their old age. They were also taught to love and respect one another.

However, the Philippine society, for the past years, has been caught up in a firestorm of change. The transition of the Philippine society from the traditional feudal, peasant, rural economy and kinship-dominated type of society is fast shaping into the modern type. The Filipino family is undergoing changes from a highly patriarchal setup to the egalitarian pattern that has developed in highly industrialized societies. The mothers assert themselves more in decision-making in the family as they contribute to its material support. The shift from a rural-agricultural economy to the urban-industrialized economy has also changed the role status of children. With parents having less and less time with children, a different kind of relationship inevitably occurs. Conflicts among members of the family and the community result from differences in opinions on how to bring up children. These changes tremendously affect the present status of the family. Several variables, such as population explosion, employment of overseas contract workers, the legal separation of husband and wife, unwed mothers, abortion, illegitimate and street children, diffusion of media, and other societal problems, have profound effects on the family. Hence, there was an emergence of a greater variety of family structures.

What impact do these changes in the family structure have on the lives of the children?

As families undergo different transitions, innumerable stress-making situations arise that affect the performance and outlook of the children. While families develop and change, they tend to work out systems of their own for dealing with everyday problems. There is no one right way to handle problems, and each person's solution is bound to be slightly different, some more effective than others. The strength to cope springs from many sources. A family that can pull together during turbulent times is likely to emerge with its members committed anew to each other and more deeply appreciative of themselves as a dynamic unit (Family Ties, 1987).

According to the family systems theory, as discussed by Olson and DeFrain (1997), everything happens to any family because family members are interconnected and operate as a group or family system. Family background profoundly influences how people think and behave, and people are best understood by understanding their families. When a child has problems, there are often problems in the family system.

As Steinberg (1987) pointed out, adolescents revert to unhealthy coping behaviors during the onset of their parent's divorce. Some of these are denial or acting as if nothing were happening; regression which is reverting to childish, immature behaviors; acting out or running away from home to show the parent that he is the one leaving home, not the parent; engaging with delinquent behaviors like taking drugs and hanging around with gangs. The author also mentioned that adolescents living in a family with single parents tend to step into the absent parent's shoes and present themselves as more mature than they are. They are more likely to get into trouble because single parents tend to be permissive. Single parents tend to grant their children more independence than other parents.

However, Steinberg also stated that the growing body of research shows that divorce, maternal employment, remarriage, and single parenthood alone do not interfere with one's psychological health and development. What matters is the quality of the parent-child relationship, not the type of family in which a child lives.

The challenge for every family, no matter its composition, is to look for and cultivate one another's strengths to equip its members with the necessary skills to cope with the demands of a growing competitive world (Marenko, 1997).

This study is anchored on Schacter's Theory of Social Comparison, stating that the individual is inclined to look to others for assistance in determining appropriate behavior. This implies that other people's way of coping with problems can serve as one's clue and consequently imitated in coping with his, hence the case of a child imitating the parent.

Family professionals maintain that there are many ways of looking at families; they, therefore, use ideas and principles from several conceptual frameworks to help them understand what is happening in the family. Five conceptual frameworks are considered valuable to family professionals: the family system theory, the family strength framework, the family development framework, the symbolic interaction framework, and the feminist framework.

As the primary social institution, the family is one of the most important agents of socialization because it teaches its members the rules and expectations for behavior in society.

It provides the care, protection, and best-loved qualities suited to teaching children the knowledge, skills, values, and norms of society. It also acts as an agent of social control, regulates sexual behavior, and is the primary reproduction unit. It gives status to members and positions in the social system. It provides financial and material security, affection, and emotional support (Zulueta, 2002).

Families may be classified as nuclear or extended based on internal organization or membership. The nuclear family typically consists of a married man and woman with their offspring. Adopted children are also considered members of the family.

The nuclear family is the primary unit of all types of families and is considered the basic building block in family structures. It is the basic unit from which all other forms of families evolve. Even in societies where complex family systems exist, the nuclear unit consisting of parents and children is recognizable and identifiable; hence, the nuclear family is generally accepted as universal. The nuclear family may be classified into two types; the family of orientation consists of the individual, his parents, and all his siblings. This is the family where the individual was born and reared. On the other hand, the family of procreation consists of the individual, his spouse, and all his children.

The family is considered extended when several nuclear families are linked by a kinship bond between parent, child, and siblings. The kinship bond makes the extended family continuous, generation after generation because each family of procreation is merged with the family of orientation.

As society undergoes changes brought about by industrialization and modern technologies, changes also occur in the family. New ideas and values tend to question traditional relationships, age and gender roles, and pattern of authority. The growth of advanced technology and migration to cities weaken family and kinship ties. The separation of members decreases daily interaction, and the more limited reciprocal ties tend to make the individual more independent of the family and the kin group.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study was conducted to determine the profile and the coping behaviors of high school students of intact and disrupted families at Cayos National High School, Cayos, Dumangas, Iloilo, and Division of Iloilo for the Academic Year 2015-2016.

The data will be obtained through a research-made questionnaire on coping behaviors and family structure. Descriptive statistics are the frequency count, means, and standard deviation, while inferential statistics are the t-test for independent samples, the Way Analysis of Variance, and Pearson's r. All inferential tests will be set at .05 alpha.

Participants/Respondents. The respondents included 120 randomly selected high school students of intact and disrupted families at Cayos National High School. They were classified according to gender, combined monthly family income, students' GPA, and birth order or rank.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher sought approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of the University of Southern Philippines Foundation. Next, the researcher sent a transmittal letter to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Iloilo, asking for permission and approval.

After the approval of the division superintendent, the questionnaires were reproduced and personally administered to the respondents, the 120 students from intact and disrupted families of Cayos NHS. They will be classified according to gender, students' GPA, combined monthly family income, and birth order or birth rank. Aside from the written instructions, instruction was supplemented for the assistance and guidance of the respondents in answering the questionnaire. They were given 20 minutes to read the direction and answer the questions.

Data Analysis Procedure. The raw data that was gathered was tallied and collated. Descriptive statistics are frequency count, means, and standard deviation, while inferential statistics employ a t-test for independent samples, the Way Analysis of Variance, and Pearson's r. All inferential tests are set at .05 alpha. All statistical computations were processed by utilizing automated statistical software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the High School Students

Table 1 shows the profile of the high school students in the aspects of gender, combined family monthly income, students' GPA, and birth order or birth rank.

Table 1. Profile of the High School Students

Profile Variables	Intact Families		Disrupted Families		COMBINED	
	n=50	%	n=50	%	n=100	%
Gender						
Male	36	72.00	9	18.00	45	45.00
Female	14	28.00	41	82.00	55	55.00
Combined Family Monthly Income						
20,001 Php and above	1	2.00	0	0.00	1	1.00
10,001 - 20,000 Php	1	2.00	0	0.00	1	1.00
5,001 - 10,000 Php	8	16.00	22	44.00	30	30.00
5,000 and below	40	80.00	28	56.00	96	96.00
Students' GPA						
95 (Outstanding)	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
90-94 (Very Satisfactory)	1	2.00	1	2.00	2	2.00
85-89 (Satisfactory)	26	52.00	11	22.00	37	37.00
80-84 (Good)	19	38.00	19	38.00	38	38.00
75-79 (Fair)	0	0.00	19	38.00	19	19.00
70-74 (Needs Much Improvement)	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
65-69 (Poor)	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00
Birth Order or Rank						
Eldest (firstborn)	8	16.00	10	20.00	18	18.00
Middle Child (second child)	28	56.00	33	66.00	61	61.00
Youngest (third child)	10	20.00	7	14.00	24	24.00
Only child	4	8.00	0	0.00	4	4.00

In terms of gender, of those from intact families, 36 were males, who make up 72% of the total 50 respondents, and 14 were females, who make up 18% of the total 50 respondents. Next, for those who come from disrupted families, 9 or 18% of the total 50 respondents were male, and 41 or 82% were females.

This information implies that most of the students from intact families are males, and most from disrupted families are females.

In terms of combined family income, for the 5,000 and below income bracket, 40 or 80% of the total population are from intact families, while 28 or 56% of the total 50 population are from disrupted families. It shows that although the families earn a meager income, they remain intact and loyal to each other. In contrast, most families with an income of 5,000 and below came from disrupted families. It is maybe because poverty or a common source of income is one of the many causes of the separation of families. For those with income of 5,001- 10,000, only 8 or 16% of the total 50 population came from intact families, and 22 or 44% came from disrupted families. As mentioned earlier, scarcity in economic needs is one of the many causes of the separation of families, and this bracket still falls below the poverty line. Next, 1 or 2% of the total population in the bracket 10,001-20,000 and above came from intact families, and 0 or 0% are from disrupted families. This data implies that those families earning a higher income are trying to preserve the sanctity of marriage and the family as the basic unit of Philippine society.

Regarding the General Point Average, 0 or 0% of students with a GPA of 70-74 came from intact and disrupted families. It is understandable because students, regardless of the structure of the family where they are, are trying very hard to pass all their subjects so that they will be promoted to the next grade/year level. Then, those with 75-70 GPA, 0 or 4 0% came from intact families, and 19 or 38% came from disrupted families. It simply shows that those students who are living with both parents, guiding them in their studies, are more likely to have higher grades, while those from disrupted families suffer problems, worries, and troubles in their studies; some of them might not be able to come up with their requirements that is why they got lower grades. For brackets 80-84, it is a tie between intact and disrupted families; both got the same score, 19 or 38% of the total 50 population. It implies that students from intact or disrupted families got the same score if the bracket 80-84 in the GPA is combined.

For the 90-94 bracket, 1 or 2% from the intact families and 1 or 2% from the disrupted families excel in the grade bracket. It means that if the student is intelligent and has a positive attitude towards his/her studies, regardless of all the stressors around him/her/, he/she can still get a high grade. For the 95 and above bracket – 0 or 0% from intact and disrupted families or no students of Cayos National High School got a grade as high as 95 and above, it is understandable because the school is small, meaning those who cannot afford to enroll in big schools and private schools are the only students who are enrolled in this school. In terms of birth order or birth rank. 4 or 8% of the intact families are the only child, and 0 or 0% from the disrupted families. This means there are students in this school who are the only child and belong to intact families, while no students who are an only child from disrupted families are enrolled. For the youngest or third child, ten students, or 20% of the total population from intact families, and 7 or 14% are from disrupted families. According to the family system process, the third child is the best purveyor of the marriage tensions and has difficulty establishing a separate identity. This may be one of the reasons that the third child of the families living in the catchment areas of Cayos National High School is enrolled in this school because they want to be with their families, and they can go home every afternoon after their classes. For middle or second child, 28 or 56% of the total population who are enrolled at Cayos National High School are from intact families, and 33 or 66% are from disrupted families. Second or middle children carry the covert emotional issues in the family and often have trouble putting together their heads and hearts. This maybe is the reason why a higher percentage of Cayos National High School enrollees is the second or middle child. It implies that these students, whether they are from intact or disrupted families, need emotional support from their parents and guardians.

For the eldest or firstborn. 8 or 16% of the intact families are firstborn, and 10 or 20% are from disrupted families. The eldest or firstborn is expected to finish his/her study first, by all means, so that the other or subsequent siblings will follow. Regardless of the family structure they are in, the parents or guardians try their best to enroll their children in a secondary school in order to have a high school diploma because the first child or the eldest carries more performance expectations than any other child due to the productivity needs of the system.

The extent of the Coping Behaviors of the High School Students

Table 2 shows the extent of coping behaviors of the two groups of respondents; those coming from intact families and those from disrupted families. In this particular component, they scored, which is interpreted as effective coping. The weighted mean for intact families is 3.01 and 3.17 for disrupted families.

This data implies that the high school students of Cayos National High School, whether from intact or disrupted families, apply effective coping strategies to all the stressors and problems that they encounter in their everyday lives and probably because it seems that; they are looking at the positive side of life and view the problems as a challenge instead of a hindrance. Perhaps it can also be said that it is instinctive for an individual to think and weigh situations when there is a need to confront stressful situations.

Although both groups employed effective coping, students from intact families talked to someone, maybe their friends, teachers, parents, or anybody they can lean on, about their problems and sought pieces of advice on the possible solutions which may be applied in order to solve the problem, then, they calm themselves by listening to music, and they look their problems in a positive way. This seems to show that they tend to focus on tension-reducing activities and submit to the belief that God will always be present to assist during times of failure and depression. While students from disrupted families' made plans of things they tend to do to solve problems and accomplish them as soon as possible, they also engaged themselves in physical activities like sports and heavy work. They gained strength in facing difficulties knowing God was always there to rescue them.

Then, spiritual support is a dominant coping behavior applied by two groups of students, possibly because of the spiritual values inculcated in the homes and the school among Christians. Filipinos are reputed for their solid spiritual beliefs and faith in God, which are a source of strength and inspiration in facing life's adversities.

Table 2. The extent of the Coping Behaviors of the High School Students

Coping Behaviors	Intact		Disrupted	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>When I have problems...</i>				
1. I Try to calm down by doing relaxation exercises and meditation.	2.78	Effective Coping	3.13	Effective Coping
2. I attend prayer retreats or recollections to strengthen my faith in God.	3.10	Effective Coping	3.25	Effective Coping
3. I engage in an activity at home like gardening and drawing to take my mind off the problem.	3.40	Very Effective Coping	3.18	Effective Coping
4. I consult with a counselor who can offer me guidance and counseling.	2.23	Less Effective Coping	2.40	Less Effective Coping
5. I seek and receive emotional comfort from members of my family.	3.18	Effective Coping	3.08	Effective Coping
6. I try to regain hope by reading the Bible or other religious books.	2.93	Effective Coping	2.68	Effective Coping
7. I calm myself by eating my favorite foods.	3.25	Effective Coping	3.55	Very Effective Coping
8. I attend stress management seminars to learn better ways to resolve problems or conflicts.	1.88	Less Effective Coping	2.50	Less Effective Coping
9. I calm myself by drinking wine, beer, or other alcoholic drinks.	1.55	Not Effective Coping	2.10	Less Effective Coping
Coping Behaviors	Intact		Disrupted	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>When I have problems...</i>				
10. I feel better if I express my anger by confronting the person who creates the problem.	2.95	Effective Coping	2.80	Effective Coping
11. I spend my time with God alone.	3.10	Effective Coping	3.10	Effective Coping
12. I take my mind off the problem by	3.28	Very Effective	3.33	Very Effective

watching TV, watching a movie, or taking a trip.		Coping		Coping
13. I try to view the problem as a challenge.	3.30	Very Effective Coping	3.18	Effective Coping
14. I try to ignore or forget the problem.	3.13	Effective Coping	3.00	Effective Coping
15. I tell myself that problem is not as complex as I thought.	3.13	Effective Coping	3.18	Effective Coping
16. I blame others when things do not turn out according to what I planned.	2.50	Less Effective Coping	2.88	Effective Coping
17. I try to avoid the problem by assuming extra responsibility.	2.65	Effective Coping	3.03	Effective Coping
18. I consult with the priest, pastor, or nun for guidance and counseling.	2.45	Less Effective Coping	2.80	Effective Coping
19. I consult my friends and seek emotional support from them.	3.50	Very Effective Coping	3.30	Very Effective Coping
20. I refuse to talk to anyone about my problem.	3.03	Effective Coping	3.18	Effective Coping
21. I just wait until the problem dies down.	2.40	Less Effective Coping	3.08	Effective Coping
22. I complain about the problem because it makes me feel better.	3.23	Effective Coping	3.35	Very Effective Coping
23. I try to find the humorous aspect of the situation and laugh at it.	2.95	Effective Coping	3.33	Very Effective Coping
24. I try to develop alternative or possible solutions by talking with persons who experienced the same problem.	3.45	Very Effective Coping	3.38	Very Effective Coping
Coping Behaviors	Intact		Disrupted	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>When I have problems...</i>				
25. I look at the problem positively.	3.78	Very Effective Coping	3.78	Very Effective Coping
26. I accept the hardship because I believe it is an appropriate punishment for my wrong actions.	3.50	Very Effective Coping	3.60	Very Effective Coping
27. I talk to someone about how I feel.	3.88	Very Effective Coping	3.63	Very Effective Coping
28. I calm myself by listening to music.	3.80	Very Effective Coping	4.10	Very Effective Coping
29. I gain strength in facing difficult situations knowing that God is always there to rescue me.	3.55	Very Effective Coping	4.13	Very Effective Coping
30. I relax by reading my favorite books and magazines.	2.93	Effective Coping	3.88	Very Effective Coping
31. I attend a support group to share and gather insights about my problems.	2.48	Less Effective Coping	3.63	Very Effective Coping
32. I lock myself in the room for a few days and refuse to talk to anyone.	2.10	Less Effective Coping	3.15	Effective Coping
33. I write my feelings in my journal or diary.	2.78	Effective Coping	3.18	Effective Coping

34. I get involved in volunteer work or community outreach programs in church and school.	3.03	Effective Coping	3.58	Very Effective Coping
35. I think that it is fate or destiny that brought me to this situation.	2.68	Effective Coping	3.70	Very Effective Coping
36. I make a list of all possible resources that I can make use of in solving problems.	2.93	Effective Coping	3.63	Very Effective Coping
37. I engage in physical activities like sports and heavy work.	3.20	Effective Coping	4.13	Very Effective Coping
38. I make plans of things that I need to do to solve the problems and soon accomplish them as soon as possible.	3.40	Very Effective Coping	4.23	Very Effective Coping
39. I consider it an opportunity to improve myself and strengthen my character.	3.50	Very Effective Coping	4.08	Very Effective Coping
40. I acknowledge my faults and try to make up for the person I am in conflict with.	3.45	Very Effective Coping	3.90	Very Effective Coping
Weighted Mean	3.01	Effective Coping	3.17	Effective Coping

Test of Significant Relationship Between the Coping

Table 3 illustrates a significant relationship between the coping behaviors of high school students and their profiles. The significance level is tested at a .05 level of significance.

Table 3. Relationship Between the Coping Behaviors of the High School Students and their Profile

Variables Correlated	r value	Computed value or t	Critical Value @ .05	Decision	Interpretation
Coping Behaviors and Gender	0.32	5.8636	1.9754	Reject the H ₀	There is a moderate correlation. (Moderate Positive Relationship)
Coping Behaviors and Combined Family Monthly Income	0.30	3.5768	1.9754	Reject the H ₀	There is a moderate correlation. (Moderate Positive Relationship)
Coping Behaviors and Students' GPA	0.28	-0.8997	1.9754	Accept the H ₀	There is no significant correlation. (Weak Positive Relationship)
Coping Behaviors and Birth Order or Rank	0.31	4.8236	1.9754	Reject the H ₀	There is a moderate correlation. (Moderate Positive Relationship)

Table 3 reveals the relationship between the coping behaviors of high school students and their profiles.

It was found that there is a moderate correlation or moderate positive relationship between the coping behaviors of high school students and their gender. This data implies that the students, regardless of their gender, have the same way of coping behaviors and are almost applying the same

strategies in coping with all the problems they encounter in their lives. However, it can be gleaned from the results that although both groups applied effective coping strategies, the male often engaged in problem-solving as their coping behavior, while the females dominantly employed spiritual support.

The combined family income and the birth order or rank of the students have a moderate positive relationship. The students, whether from intact or disrupted families and regardless of the combined family income and birth order or rank, cope with their problems effectively.

Regarding coping behaviors and students' GPA, the results revealed no significant correlation or positive relationship.

Table 1 shows that more students from intact families have a GPA of 80-84 and 85-89, and more students from disrupted families have a GPA of &5-79 and 80-84. Students from intact families appear to utilize several ways of handling problems. This may represent a constructive style of coping characterized by working on a problem while remaining optimistic, fit, relaxed, and socially connected. At the same time, those students from disrupted families with low GPAs tend to work out ways of coping with pressures at home and in school. They utilized relaxation and spiritual support. This shows that instead of focusing on improving their academic standing, they tend to focus on tension-reducing activities.

Test of Significant Difference in the Coping Behaviors of the High School Students

Table 4 presents the result of the test of significant differences in the coping behaviors of the high school students when grouped according to their gender, combined family monthly income, students' GPA, and birth order or rank.

Table 4. The difference in the Coping Behaviors of the Students

Profile	Group	Mean	SD	T	CV@.05	Decision	Interpretation
Gender	Intact	102.3	11.8	2.50	2.0017	Reject the H_0	There is a significant difference.
	Disrupted	95.03	10.74				
Family Monthly Income	Intact	89.73	15.27	0.39	2.0017	Do not reject H_0	There is no significant difference.
	Disrupted	88.13	16.78				
Students' GPA	Intact	99.27	10.31	2.51	2.0017	Reject the H_0	There is a significant difference.
	Disrupted	92.43	10.84				
Birth Order or Rank	Intact	102.5	7.24	1.6	2.0017	Do not reject H_0	There is no significant difference.
	Disrupted	98.8	9.16				

The results showed a significant difference in the coping behavior of the high school students from intact and disrupted families when grouped according to their gender and students' GPA. At the same time, there is no significant difference in the coping behavior of the High School students from intact and disrupted families when grouped according to their family monthly income and birth order/rank.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn.

First, most of the students from intact families are males, and most of the students from disrupted families are females.

Second, the respondents from intact and disrupted families, regardless of their grades, combined family monthly income, and birth order or birth rank, have a moderate correlation or

moderate positive relationship. In contrast, the students' coping behaviors and GPA have a weak positive relationship.

Third, Cayos National High School students, regardless of whether they are from intact or disrupted families, employ effective coping behaviors to all the stressors, problems, and challenges they encounter in their everyday lives. It is a positive attitude; they view their problems as a challenge, not a hindrance.

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